

EMERGING ISSUES IN FINANCIAL SECTOR REFORMS AND THE FUTURE OF INDIAN ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

Indian's financial system has long been inadequate with an economy worth \$ 2 trillion; the country's financial flaws are increasingly serious. The India's growth story although impacted to a great extent by global factors is equally driven by domestic factors. In view of growing integration with global markets, India needs a strong regulatory framework to prevent and protect against external threat and in the meantime grow its economy significantly.

The objective of present paper is to examine the emerging financial sector reforms in the light of ongoing global financial crisis right since US financial crisis and its gradual impact on India in particular. Keeping in view with the above grave dimensions, the present paper is divided into three parts. Part I presents an Introductory background on financial sector reforms in India since emergence of New Indian Economic Policy in 1991 and its gradual sectoral benchmarking of reforms at international level particularly US subprime crisis in 2008 and its operation policies implemented in Indian financial sector to overcome the impact of international financial crisis. Part II mainly concentrate on Indian financial sector and its benchmarking of reforms in connection with strong operational condition, the weak grounds, the opportunities and the impending threat on re-emergence of International Financial Crisis. Part III highlights the present and future policy perspectives of Indian financial sector reforms and its impact on service sector of Indian economy. The last part provides aggregative conclusion and some effective line of direction to keep Indian financial sector to its positive health from the angle of future.

Key words: Economic Policy, financial flaws, Financial Crisis

Part I :An Introductory background on financial sector reforms in India since emergence of New Indian Economy Policy in 1991 and its gradual sectoral benchmarking of reforms at international level particularly US sub-prime crisis in 2008 and its operation policies implemented in Indian financial sector to overcome the impact of international financial crisis.

Indian financial sector is diversified and expanding rapidly. It consists of commercial banks, insurance companies, non-banking financial companies, Co-operatives, pension funds, mutual funds, and other smaller financial entities. Our financial system is dominated by banks and it accounts for over 60% of total assets of financial system followed by insurance¹. The regulation and supervision of financial system in India is marked by different regulatory authorities as shown below:-

The financial system that we have today is the result of the financial sector reforms that started in the year 1991 with the policy of economic liberalization, privatization and globalization under the flagship of the then Finance Minister of India, Dr. Manmohan Singh. Since then a package of reforms were adopted which was able to cope with the short comings that were then evident. At that time, the role of the financial system was restricted to channeling of resources from surplus to deficit sectors. Later on progress was made in other areas also like reduction in capital controls so that Indian firms could access to foreign capital for developmental projects along with creation of new contribution pension system so that young population could enjoy benefits in due course of time. Similarly creation of a new insurance regulator i.e. IRDA (Insurance Regulation and Development Agency) and ending of public sector monopolies in the

field by inviting private players in this field was also done. And lastly, creation of an organized equity market by establishing new regulator “SEBI” and new infrastructure institutions i.e. the NSE and National Securities Depository.

These phases of reforms that started in 1991 are continuing till now. However a large number of problems with the financial system remain unresolved. It is because most of the existing financial laws in India e.g. RBI Act (1934), Insurance Act (1938) etc were enacted, when the country was a command and control economy. They are guided by the objective of containing and controlling financial markets and banning activity rather than supervising and regulating market. But in spite of these loopholes prevalent in Indian financial system (as discussed later in Part II of this article), India was able to somewhat withheld the disruptions of global financial crisis of 2009 mainly due to robust regulatory and supervisory framework, limited openness and global exposure of banking system and timely policy action especially to manage liquidity. However, despite these, it needs continuous improvement in regulation, supervision and stability areas in order to avoid any mishappening in near future.

Part II: Indian financial system and its SWOT Analysis

India’s financial system was able to withhold the impact of financial crisis of U.S.A. though there happened to be slow-down in the Indian economy. It is possible because of the Bank dominated financial system of our country which is strictly monitored and governed by our country’s central bank. R.B.I. through its strong regulatory and supervisory regime consisting of higher than minimum capital requirements, frequent hands on comprehensive onsite inspection , a conservative liquidity risk policy and restrictions on bank’s capacity to take on more volatile exposures is able to cope with the impact of US financial crisis on Indian economy. This is the strength of India’s financial system. However, still India lacks financial inclusions. It has a tough task of reaching out to customers who don’t have any access to saving account, pension or other sort of financial service. Though the current N.D.A government at the centre through its policy of “Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojna” is able to speed up towards the policy of financial inclusion but still India’s financial system has many deficiencies.

India has the second largest population of people who are above the age of 60 in the world and this number is expected to touch 173million by 2026 from 71 million in 2014 ². So the task of covering this segment in some kind of pension and social welfare schemes is a mammoth task before financial institutions of India. Apart from this, India’s working population in the age bracket of 15-59 years accounts for 57% of overall population ³. These all things are associated with India’s domestic market. Apart from these, it should adopt the policy of expansion of India’s bank in

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overseas market to tap the foreign clients like mid size companies that don't have access neither to capital market nor to foreign banks for funding their various developmental projects as enjoyed by their big counterparts. So there lie a lot of opportunities for Indian financial institutions not only in domestic market but also in foreign markets as well. If we do the "SWOT Analysis" of India's Financial System then steps could be taken in tapping the opportunities ahead and also rectifying the weakness of India's current financial system and formulation of measures for impending the threat in near future to India's economy. By doing "SWOT Analysis" of the Indian financial system we could derive the following conclusions:-

Strength of Indian financial system

1. Strong Regulatory and supervisory framework.
2. Gradual approach towards capital account convertibility.
3. Prudence in opening of banking sectors to private and foreign banks.
4. Limited openness and global exposure of banking system.
5. Strict norms for securitization.
6. Stringent norms on exposure to sensitive sectors.
7. Pre-emptive action with respect to housing, consumer and real-estate credit.
8. Prudential norms in Inter banks borrowing.
9. Bank dominated financial system.

Weakness of Indian financial system

1. Most of the existing financial laws are very outdated and were enacted when our economy was a controlled one.
2. Lack of financial inclusion.
3. Lack of financial stability.
4. Lack of accountability of financial agencies for their failures.
5. Formation of multiple regulators often leading to regulatory arbitrage. e.g Mutual funds regulated by SEBI and ULIP's by IRDA.
6. Challenges of International Financial Integration (Basel-III).
7. Growth of unregulated shadow financial system
8. Rise of numerous ponzi schemes.
9. Lack of financial awareness.

Opportunities of Indian financial system

1. Tapping of under- penetrated Indian financial market.
2. The rapid speed of urbanization in India has led to creation of housing and infrastructure investment opportunities for financial institutions.
3. Increasing reach and scalability of financial services beyond Tiers I and Tier II cities with the help of Technology.
4. India's rich demographic dividend.
5. Rapid expansion and increasing inter connectivity with fast growing markets of South America, Asia, Africa and Middle East posing opportunities for Indian financial institutions to move there.
6. Providing customized services to Indian consumers by financial institution.

Threat to Indian financial system

1. Fiscal Pressure
2. Political and social instability of our country.

3. Growing integration with global market.
4. Current account deficit.
5. Inflation

Part III: The present and future policy perspectives of Indian financial sector reforms

As seen from the above parts, there still remains certain loopholes in Indian financial system, which needs to be rectified and also it should adopt global financial standards like implementation of Basel III norms in India at the earliest which aims at ensuring financial stability by maintaining higher capital standard. In today's world, since the whole world is integrated hence the occurrence of financial turmoil in one country can affect other countries also, especially, if the country is advance one as seen in case of U.SA. Under certain circumstances, India needs to have a strong regulatory framework to prevent and protect against any external financial threats. Apart from this, it should be able to tap the opportunities prevailing in foreign countries like SAAAME (South America, Asia, Africa and Middle East) and in our country as well. We should not forget that India is a country with consistently highly level of saving of nearly 30%⁴. But unfortunately most of the savings of the household sector goes into buying gold and real-estate. Hence the urgency of the situation demands that now these savings could be channeled into the capital market so that, on one hand, investors can enjoy the benefits and on the other hand, the economy can flourish by using investors capital in various infrastructure and developmental projects along with requirement of necessary capital for corporate in order to carry out their own expansion and country's progress.

Therefore the role of financial institution is huge so that it could innovate simpler financial products and promote the source by use of smart technology and support for financial literacy as well.

In order to eliminate the deficiencies prevailing in the current Indian financial sectors, a new draft of law i.e. Indian Finance Code (IFC) has already been done which is currently debated in public domain. The new draft of Indian Financial Code (IFC) which will perhaps be enacted after 2015, when it will be passed by the Indian Parliament. This new set of financial sector reforms law is the result of recommendations of four expert committee's reports namely on International Finance laid by Percy Mistry in 2007, Domestic Finance laid by Raghuram Rajan in 2008, Capital Control laid by U.K. Sinha in 2010 and Consumer Protection laid by Dhirendra Swarup in 2010. They all suggested for reforms in current financial sector. Soon after their reports, India's Ministry of Finance set up the Financial Sector Legislative Reforms Commission under flagship of retired judge of the Supreme Court, Justice B.N. Srikrishna to formulate the new financial sector norms and the end result is Indian Financial Code (IFC). When it will come into existence then perhaps the country will achieve high growth in future and it might reduce impact of any global as well as domestic risk in near future.

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